

WARIACYJNOŚĆ WYPEŁNIENIA TREŚCIĄ KRAJOWEJ WIEDZY PRZYRODNICZEJ W PRZEKROJU NAJLEPSZYCH ŚWIATOWYCH TRADYCJI OŚWIATOWYCH (IX - XIX w.)

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Adnotacja. Artykuł porusza problematykę z zakresu wariacyjności treści krajowej wiedzy przyrodniczej, która została zdeterminowana przez wydarzenia historyczne z IX-XIX w., co miało wpływ na dalszy całościowy rozwój oświaty. Omówiono wpływ idei bizantyjsko-europejskiej na zainteresowanie determinantą społeczno-kulturową, która odzwierciedlała się w dyferencjacji przedmiotowej procesu naukowo-wychowawczego we współczesnych granicach terytorium ukraińskiego.

Przedmiotem badań było treściowe napełnienie krajowej wiedzy przyrodniczej w przekroju najlepszych światowych tradycji oświatowych w wyznaczonym okresie historycznym.

Celem artykułu jest przeanalizowanie wariacyjnej treści krajowej wiedzy przyrodniczej poprzez pryzmat światowych tradycji oświatowych z IX-XIX w.

Metodologicznym instrumentem badań była metodyka biograficzna, chronologiczno-treściowa, etapowo-problematyczna, historyczno-genetyczna, historyczno-pedagogiczna oraz porównawcza.

Zaznaczono ścisły związek faktu historycznego przyjęcia chrześcijaństwa z pogłębieniem przyrodniczego napełnienia wiedzy, co zostało uwarunkowane przez szereg potrzeb obiektywnych: terytorialne rozszerzenie religii światowej, bliskie międzyetniczne kontakty, nawiązanie relacji handlowych, pogłębienie związków dyplomatycznych między państwami, reforma oświaty i kultury. W autorskim podejściu zwrócono uwagę na szczegółową analizę bogactwa danych informacyjnych wykorzystywanych w procesach naukowo-wychowawczych, które w głównej mierze czerpano z dawnych zabytków i ksiązek historycznych włączonych do procesu oświatowego.

Analiza problematyki tytułowej została ukształtowana w oparciu o analizę najlepszych historyczno-pedagogicznych personaliów badanej epoki, którzy zajmowali się problematyką wysokiej ideowości poglądów pedagogicznych i przekonań współczesnych naukowców. Ponowne przemyślenie wyznaczonego przedmiotu realizowano poprzez uwzględnienie całościowej, aksjologicznej, humanistycznej oraz osobowościowo zorientowanej konstrukcji badań.

Uwaga badawcza autora została skoncentrowana na odzwierciedleniu stopniowego rozwoju wiedzy przyrodniczej poprzez pryzmat samorealizacji osobistej, pobudowanie wzajemnego działania przedstawicieli inteligencji krajowej ze światem zewnętrznym.

Na poziomie teoretycznym uogólniono, iż inicjatywa społeczna progresywnych elit krajowych aktualizowała zagadnienie dotyczące masowej alfabetyzacji, praktycznego ukierunkowania treściowego napełnienia procesu naukowo-wychowawczego, niezbędność zastosowania nowych instytucji oświatowych na terytorium różnych jednostek administracyjno-terytorialnych naszego państwa. Odnotowano, iż taki progresywizm poglądowy dość często był tłumiony przez działające kierownictwo polityczne, jednak mimo to nie zrujnował się pod wpływem procesów z tamtych czasów.

Zauważono ścisły związek pomiędzy genezą krajowej wiedzy przyrodniczej, a tendencjami rozwoju najlepszych światowych tradycji oświatowych. Udowodniono, iż

zainteresowanie przyrodnicze krajowego dorobku twórczego ówczesnych myślicieli odzwierciedlało szczytną ideę treści organizacji procesu oświatowego, napełnionego faktami o państwie. Taka trajektoria rozwoju rzeczywistości oświatowej dała możliwość wszechstronnego rozwoju osobowości, jej rozwój zawodowy i ukierunkowanie do rozwoju aktualnego wówczas państwowotwórczego zagadnienia. Podkreślono praktyczne ukierunkowanie oraz znaczenie wiedzy przyrodniczej dla pogłębionego uświadomienia fizyczno-geograficznych osobliwości miejscowości rodzimej, co łączono w badanym okresie z wychowaniem w duchu patriotycznym i estetycznym.

Słowa kluczowe: treściowe napełnienie, geneza, nauki przyrodnicze, tradycje oświatowe.

CONTENT VARIABILITY OF DOMESTIC NATURAL KNOWLEDGE IN THE LIGHT OF THE BEST WORLD EDUCATIONAL TRADITIONS (IX – XIX centuries)

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Abstract. The issue of the article addresses the variability of the content of natural science knowledge, which was accumulated during the IX - XIX centuries, during the progressive development of domestic education. The influence of the origins of the ideology of European humanism on the orientation of socio-cultural determinants, which was reflected in the development of education and the differentiation of the educational process content, is detailed.

The subject of the study is the content of the domestic natural sciences in the context of the best world educational traditions of the designated historical period.

The purpose of the article is to analyze the varied content of the national natural sciences through the prism of the world educational traditions of the IX - XIX centuries.

The research tools for the study were the biographical, chronological and content, incremental, historical and genetic, historical-pedagogical and comparative methods.

The analysis of the titled problem was based on the analysis of the best theoretical developments of the epoch under study, which challenged the high ideology of the pedagogical views and beliefs of contemporaneous Enlighteners. The rethinking of the studied problem was based on the consideration of a holistic axiological, humanistic, and personally oriented structure of the study.

The author's research attention is paid to reconsidering the progressive development of natural sciences through the prism of personal self-realization, building close interaction between representatives of the domestic intelligentsia and the outside world.

The author's view focuses on the natural saturation of informational data for the educational process of this period, taken mainly from ancient sources and historical books widely involved in the educational process. The close correlation between the historical fact of the converting to Christianity and the deepening of the natural sciences content, which was due to the objective need for the territorial expansion of the stated world religion, close interethnic communication, the establishment of trade relations, deepening of diplomatic relations between the states, reformation of education and the cultural sphere in general.

On the theoretical level, it has been summarized that the social initiative of the progressive national elite actualized the issue of mass literacy, the practical orientation of the educational process content, the need for the establishment of new educational institutions in the territory of various regional administrative subdivisions of our state. It is noted that such progressiveness of views often suffered considerable harassment on the part of the current political leaders of that time, but did not devalue under the influence of destructive processes.

The close connection between the genesis of the national natural sciences and the tendencies of development of the best world educational traditions is highlighted. It is proved that the natural orientation of the national creative works of contemporary thinkers reflected the highly adaptive nature of the educational process organization, which was filled with natural science data. Such a trajectory of the development of educational reality enabled the full development of an individual, his further professional success and commitment to the solution of the national issue that was relevant at that time. The importance of natural sciences for a more profound rethinking of the physical and geographical features of their native land, which was correlated in the period under study with patriotic and aesthetic education, was emphasized.

Keywords: content, genesis, natural sciences, educational traditions.

ВАРІАТИВНІСТЬ ЗМІСТОВОЇ НАПОВНЕНОСТІ ВІТЧИЗНЯНИХ ПРИРОДНИЧИХ ЗНАТЬ У РОЗРІЗІ КРАЩИХ СВІТОВИХ ОСВІТНІХ ТРАДИЦІЙ (IX – XIX ст.)

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Анотація. Проблематика статті торкається варіативності змісту вітчизняних природничих знань, які детермінувалися історичною подією IX – XIX ст. та позначилися на поступальному розвитку освіти в цілому. Деталізовано вплив візантійсько - європейської ідейності на подальшу зорієнтованість соціокультурних детермінант, які віддзеркалювалися у предметній диференціації навчально-виховного процесу в сучасних межах української території.

Предметом дослідження виступила змістова наповненість вітчизняних природничих знань у розрізі кращих світових освітніх традицій означеного історичного періоду.

Метою статті є аналіз варіативного змісту вітчизняних природничих знань крізь призму світових освітніх традицій IX – XIX ст.

Методологічним інструментарієм дослідження послуговував біографічний, хронологічно-змістовний, поетапно-проблемний, історико-генетичний, історико-педагогічний та порівняльний методи.

Підкреслено тісний взаємозв'язок історичного факту прийняття християнства із поглибленням природничої наповненості знань, що обумовлювалося низкою об'єктивних потреб: територіального поширення світової релігії, тісного міжнаціонального спілкування, налагодження торговельних відносин, поглиблення дипломатичних зв'язків між державами, реформування освіти та культурної сфери. Авторський погляд звернено на детальний аналіз природничої насиченості інформаційних даних для навчально-виховного процесу цього періоду, які черпалися в основному із давніх пам'яток та історичних книг, широко залучених до освітнього процесу.

Аналіз титульної проблематики засновувався на аналізі кращих історико-педагогічних персоналій досліджуваної епохи, які проблематизували високоідейність педагогічних поглядів та переконань тогочасних просвітників. Переосмислення визначеного предмету будувалося на врахуванні цілісного аксіологічного, гуманістичного та особистісно зорієнтованого конструкту дослідження.

Дослідницька увага автора зосереджувалася на відрефлексуванні поступального розвитку природничих знань крізь призму особистісної самореалізації, побудови тісної взаємодії представників вітчизняної інтелігенції із зовнішнім світом.

На теоретичному рівні узагальнено, що соціальна ініціативність прогресивної вітчизняної еліти актуалізувала на порядку денному питання масової грамотності,

практичної зорієнтованості змістового наповнення навчально-виховного процесу, необхідності заснування нових освітніх інституцій на території різних адміністративно-територіальних одиниць нашої держави. Зауважено, що така прогресивність поглядів нерідко зазнавала значних утисків зі сторони діючого політичного керівництва, проте не девальгувалася під впливом руйнівних процесів того часу.

Відрефлексовано тісний взаємозв'язок генезису вітчизняних природничих знань із тенденціями розвитку кращих світових освітніх традицій. Доведено, що природнича зорієнтованість вітчизняних творчих доробків тогочасних мислителів віддзеркалювала високоідейність змісту організації освітнього процесу, наповненого красназвочою фактажністю. Така траєкторія розвитку освітньої реальності уможлиблювала всебічний розвиток особистості, її подальшу професійну успішність та цілеспрямованість до розв'язання актуального на той час питання власного державотворення. Підкреслено практичну зорієнтованість та значущість природничих знань для все більш глибокого переосмислення фізико-географічних особливостей рідної місцевості, що співвідносилось у досліджуваний період із патріотичним та естетичним вихованням.

Ключові слова: змістова наповненість, генезис, природничі науки, освітні традиції.

Introduction. The need for reform of the educational sphere on the principles of humanism and democracy, which has come to a halt today in the context of the demographic crisis, is increasingly actualizing the problem of the diversification of the content of the existing educational process. In order to solve the existing socio-cultural destruction in a holistic way, it is necessary to turn to the first sources of valuable historical and pedagogical ideas of domestic thinkers of different historical epochs, whose contribution to the modern socio-cultural treasury of our state is, in fact, invaluable. In such research approach, the axiological dimensions of interdisciplinary knowledge should be based on global trends in development (in particular, STEM Education).

Some aspects of the problem under study are found in the works of V. Andrushchenko, O. Sukhomlyns'ka, T. Zavgorodnaya, V. Syrotyuk, P. Gusak, T. Dudka and others. However, the question of the natural variation of knowledge in the context of the best educational traditions of certain centuries requires further study.

The purpose of the article is to analyze the varied content of the national natural sciences through the prism of the world educational traditions of the IX – XIX centuries.

According to the purpose, the main objectives of the study are defined as following (*the task*):

- to analyze the state of the investigated problem;
- to follow the peculiarities of the pedagogical theory and practice development during the researched historical epoch;
- to publicize national historical and pedagogical experience.

The research tools for the study were the biographical, chronological and content, incremental, historical and genetic, historical-pedagogical and comparative *methods*.

Historical and pedagogical preconditions of the IX - XIII centuries. An insight into the development of regional problems in the genesis of historical and pedagogical phenomena is a necessary tool for modernizing the content and improving the quality of education in each region of Ukraine. To get an objective characteristic of the preconditions that contributed to the formation of a particular pedagogical phenomenon or process, one should thoroughly analyze the social and cultural, and organizational preconditions prevailing on the territory of our state within the studied period.

Consideration of the historical and typological aspects of the development of natural sciences reflected some specific directions of the university education development in particular regions of Ukraine. The discovery of the natural sciences genesis in terms of higher education became possible under the conditions of analysis of its essence, preconditions of formation, peculiarities of organization, and trends of development.

Natural knowledge was formed when the experienced generation realized the need to impart the knowledge about the peculiarities of their native land to the youth and correlated the issue with the basis of the patriotism development. Knowledge of the regional nature was an integral part of the traditional culture. An indication of this is the focus of folk rituals, customs, and holidays on the upbringing of children respectful of the nature of the region. Over time, the natural sciences acquired a more profound scientific content and turned into an independent branch of knowledge. Its practical implementation is the result of hard work of the galaxy of scientists and educators.

A significant influence on the development of natural sciences was the scientific data of chronicles and state documents that existed in the days of Kyiv Rus (IX-XIII centuries). Such data were applied and they served as a systematic informational and natural resource.

The accumulation of natural science in Kyiv Rus was under the influence of a number of prerequisites, including the establishment of a land property institute, the dominance of agriculture, the formation of trade connections, the influence of the pre-Christian and Christian vectors, the development of literacy and education, the establishment of libraries and icon painting schools.

In the first Ukrainian pedagogical references, there were many generalized materials of natural sciences. These include the Initial Chronicle (up to 1111). It featured such a characteristic: "... the territory of Kyiv Rus has its own soils, eternal, parental, grand-parental, purchased, that is, the fields, forests and hayfields, ponds and mills, and all other sorts of things ..." (Velychko, 1991). Even such a brief description opens to the reader all the greatness and natural wealth of the Ukrainian land.

The Kyiv Chronicle (up to 1200 years) stated: "And the city of Kyiv ... from the other side of the Dnieper River, which... is famous for the soils, forests and all kinds of arable land ..." (Myshanych, 1989). These chronicles are informative because they reflect the geographical location of the city and the level of development of natural resources.

The Galician-Volyn Chronicle (1201–1292) contained the following descriptions: "... and the outcrop and the rocks near Chernihiv ... on the rivers where there are the waterways to the cities, they did not construct the dams to make the grain supplies transportation possible..." (Myshanych, 1989). This passage indicates that at that time the natural descriptions were much generalized, informative and used as a summary land management report.

The "Tale of bygone years" chronicle contained such nature related materials: "And in that land, where the city of Kyiv, with its... cities and towns..., and also on the other bank of the Dnieper and Chernihiv ..." (Myshanych, 1989). These descriptions served as a unique verbal map, which described the locations of cities and the adjoined territories.

In the "Lay of Ihor's warfare", there was a description of the variety of birds (54) and rivers (23), while the "Russ Chronicle" listed 70 towns in Volyn alone (Lychacheva, 1985).

The chronicles content shows that the authors of those times were well aware of their own land as well as of the territory geography. In the first written references, the attention is paid not only to the descriptions of the all-Ukrainian events but also to the facts of local life, which contained the nature description.

The written piece "The life and pilgrimage of Danyl, a hegumen of the Russ land", a Chernihiv monk gave the comparison of the Palestinian river Jordan and the Chernihiv river Snov: "... Jordan is like the river of Snov in terms of width, and in terms of depth, and it flows steeply and swiftly like the river of Snov ... In the mouth, the Jordan is as wide as the Snov ... On the Jordan banks, there are a lot of willow-like trees, though it is not our willow, it's only somehow similar to the shrub ... " (Voznyak, 1992). Similar essays were written by the clergy to spread education among the local population.

The opening of theological educational institutions (seminaries) and secular schools made a positive influence on the development of natural sciences in Slobozhanshchyna and Left-Bank Ukraine in the late XVIII – early XVIII centuries. This was caused by the fact that at that time the Christian religion was dominant in the formation of culture and education. From 1877 to 1884, the rector of the Podilsky Seminary, an Archpriest Mytrofan Symashkevich, together with his students, collected interesting materials of the natural content and published the works as follows: "Podillya Territory", "Historical and Ethnographic sketch of Podillya."

The historic transition from Kyiv Rus (IX-XIII centuries) to the Galician-Volyn Kingdom (XIII-XIV centuries) and the Cossack age (XVI-XVIII centuries) was marked by significant changes in the social, economic, political, cultural and educational spheres. These changes also affected the development of domestic natural knowledge. The fourteenth and eighteenth centuries clearly outlined the following organizational and socio-cultural trends of its development: penetration of the ideas of European humanism, pedagogical in particular, into the territory of Ukraine; the emergence and development of its own printing craft, which encouraged the dynamic spread of the natural knowledge and information; the emergence of new artistic genres, for example, portraying the local landscapes.

The source of natural sciences in the above-mentioned historical period was the county and territorial books, which were widely used in the educational process. There we can find the information about the origin of manufacture in Ukraine, the boundaries of settlements, and so on.

Characteristic features of the XIV-XVIII centuries. During the period of the Zaporizhzhian Sich, the people with a high level of geographical knowledge of the surrounding area enjoyed great respect among the local population as well as outside the state.

In the XVI century, the founder of the Sich Hetman Dmytro Baida-Vyshnevetsky collected the geographic information about the lower and middle flows of the Dnieper, the right bank of the Don, and handed them to the compilers of the first Russian map "Book on the Big drawing", which was published in 1627. As a result, the name of the Hetman entered the history of the scientific discovery of the Dnieper basin.

In the XVI-XVII centuries, the teachers of brother schools were well known for the high level of pedagogical skill: they were able to combine theoretical material (built on the child's experience) with the practical activities. The material was taught in the form of conversations with students and it was later on applied in practice by means of

independent observations of the regional. The current textbooks were supplied with the data from the regional history and ethnographic material. The fundamentals of natural sciences, which were taught in brother schools, had a significant impact on the development of national culture and self-awareness. It should be noted that such an educational system is viewed through the prism of national ethnography, which is a part of the national ethnographic study.

Ivan Vyshensky cared about imparting of the natural knowledge to the students. The author wrote: "And what comes from this land, where there are mountains, ... weeds, herbs, flowering herbs, I did not have to send anything to you in a gift, then I thought ... three ... flowers ... I am sending to your grace. These one - because the flowers are very needed, as an example or an image for the students ..." (Lyubar, 2003).

In the XVII-XVIII centuries, the social and cultural trends of the development of natural sciences emerged. They were the following: 1) thematic descriptions became an integral part of the state documents; 2) the criterion of the level of spiritual culture became education and science (including literacy); 3) Kyiv-Mohyla Academy turns into the main educational center of the natural sciences dissemination.

The founder of Kyiv-Mohyla Academy, Petro Mohyla made a significant contribution to the natural education of young people. In his work, "Anthology that is the prayers and education is useful for the soul. In the mental usefulness of the students and all the devotional ones saying the prayers" (K., 1636) the educator noted that due to the feeling of love for the land, the students formed an integral view of their ethnic belonging and genetic connection of the generations. It is worth noting that the scientist was one of the first to found the park area in the city of Kyiv (Siropolko, 2001).

The materials of the purchase certificate (1602) depict the landscape of the Southern Polissya at the beginning of the XVII century: "... with the islands of animals and birds, ponds, bridges ... rivers ... marshes ..." (Belozerskaya, 1898).

Bishop Yakiv Susha was one of the first naturalists of the Kholmshchyna. In his work "Phoenix" (1646), which was well-known in the scientific circles of that time, the author stated: "... the land of the Kholm flows with the streams, lives with the springs, abundant with ponds, famous for lakes, the rivers Bug and Vepr to Gdansk, Prypyat and Turia in the Polish distant lands, it sails its abundance to the Dnieper, in the end, it sufficiently decorates itself with meadows and forests" (Voznyak, 1992)

The hieromonk Mykhailo Losytsky was spreading the local knowledge all his life and was telling the students about the innate ability of each person to love his country. In the preface to the copy of the Gustyn Chronicle (1670), we can find the following words: "... every person has some kind of lust and love for the motherland and native land; it draws everyone like a magnet-stone to the iron ... " (Grinberg, 1999). The author further asserts that only due to the hard work of people who were not indifferent to the fate of the region, we have valuable written reminders about nature, because in the first place they cared about the fact that "when they are gone, the coming generation ... won't have the bygone things left unknown" (Grinberg, 1999). According to the hieromonk, if there were no chronicles, then "... without knowledge, everything would go to the ground together with the body, and people, as if in the darkness, would not know what had happened in the past" (Grinberg, 1999).

The book of Guillaume de Boplan "Description of Ukraine" (1650) describes how the regional nature contributed to the victory of the Cossacks "... no Pole could find out about this place" (Boplan, 1990). By this statement, the author sought to emphasize that

the thematic knowledge was passed from generation to generation and was a national value.

Historical and pedagogical variability of the XIX century. Ever since ancient times, the Ukrainian people have been educated in the traditions of previous generations. This includes the pedagogical tradition of sharing the knowledge verbally about the native land, its wealth and people. The above-mentioned tradition was a part of natural sciences, which evolved through the active educational activities of the Ukrainian people. It is clear why the Chumaks were very well educated about the local lore. When they were traveling to Crimea for salt, they did not have to wander the paths of the steppe, because their landmarks were rivers, beams, graves, and the like.

A. Kozachkovsky's memoirs about the great Kobzar of Ukraine T. Shevchenko serve as the confirmation of the tradition to share natural-oriented knowledge verbally. The author wrote that during the trip to Pereyaslav, Taras Grygorovych "... quickly became acquainted with local fishermen ... and was extremely interested in everything connected with Ukraine, its past, its history, folk art ..." (Kozachkovskyj, 1982)

D. Yavornytsky in his work "The History of the Zaporizhzhya Cossacks" noted that the Cossacks were so educated that even "among the ... woody islands, the swamps, among the impenetrable and non-transparent reeds" they were well oriented in the surrounding area and won numerous victories (Yavornyczkyj, 1990). This indicates that the natural sciences had an extremely important practical significance in public life.

Development of the domestic natural sciences in the XIX century contributed to the functioning of provincial scholarly archival commissions, which started in 1844. The purpose of their activities was to collect, process and preserve the archival sources. Commissions that worked in Ukrainian provinces turned into the centers of local lore work. Within the period of their operation (until 1918), they issued more than 500 copies of periodicals and collections.

T. Shevchenko was a member of the Kyiv Provincial Archival Commission. Presenting unique landscapes, beauty, greatness, and history of the native land to the public, he was able to show the harmony of man with the land. The poet believed a person to be educated and high-minded if he passionately loves his homeland, his country where he was born and lives. Based on the ethnographic approach, his creative work became a kind of driving force of difficult national revival. T. Shevchenko's "Picturesque Ukraine" album was very educative. He depicted "... the views that are available in Ukraine, remarkable of whether history or beauty ... as the people live ... as he once was living and doing" (Shevchenko, 1964). The motive that inspired Kobzar to the creation of this masterpiece was the desire to make the prominent places of his homeland, which he called "Picturesque Ukraine" better known (Shevchenko, 1964).

During the XIX century, natural knowledge proved itself a rather complex social and cultural phenomenon. The interest in knowing the homeland increased significantly and was revealed in the creation of museums, and deployment of the movement, which was called a motherland science (Razmustova, 1999). The Russian Geographical Society established the center for its development in 1845, where the Commission for the description of provinces of the Kyiv educational district was founded. It made a major contribution to the development of domestic natural sciences. In schools, the subject of ethnographic study (motherland science) was introduced, and it was the beginning of the development of the school natural cycle.

As a conclusion. Having analyzed the above-mentioned, we can see the formation of the first educational and natural initiatives in Ukraine, the only task was to comprehensively explore the native land and "equip" the younger generation with the necessary border knowledge with the help of social forces. The activities of science and education representatives were carried out despite the lack of authority support at that time. Working independently in different parts of Ukraine, local circles of scientists and educators turned into the "academies of sciences on the ground". An example is the transformation of the Commission for the description of provinces of the Kyiv educational district into the Southwest Department of the Russian Geographical Society, which dealt with the accumulation of natural knowledge as well as its application in the educational process. The department became the first organization of Ukrainian study in Ukraine, which contemporary domestic and foreign teachers consider as a prototype of the National Academy of Sciences. All these steps were taken thanks to the hard work of millions of native educators who sought to impart the most valuable treasure that is the knowledge about their native land, to the young people.

Prospects of the further researches are seen in the study of the axiological content of the creative heritage of pedagogical personnel's, who have made a significant contribution to the development of higher education in various regions of the world.

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